

A Novel Approach based on Recurrent Neural Networks Applied to Adaptive Beamforming

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Embedding artificial intelligence into current communication systems will substantially assist the development of ecosystems beyond 5G. In this study, a new neural network (NN) approach applied to antenna array adaptive beamforming is presented. A Recurrent NN (RNN) based on the Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) architecture is used as a beamformer in order to receive the angles of arrival (AoA) of incoming signals and produce the complex weights for the feeding of the elements of the antenna array. These weights are subsequently compared with the respective weights derived by a null steering beamforming (NSB) algorithm to measure the accuracy of the RNN. The proposed RNN utilizes four hidden GRU layers and one extra layer for linear transformation. The RNN training is performed by using a large data set derived from a realistic antenna array using NSB as the beamforming technique. The RNN performance is tested using the root mean square error (RMSE) metric, whereas its beamforming performance is evaluated by estimating the mean deviation of the main lobe and null directions from their respective desired directions. A comparison between various NN structures and an overall study of the proposed RNN-based beamformer are also presented.

Index Terms—Adaptive arrays, Antenna Arrays, Feedforward neural networks, Recurrent neural networks

I. INTRODUCTION

MODERN wireless communications demand faster and more reliable networks. From estimating the angle of arrival (AoA) of incoming signals to producing the desired radiation pattern, intelligent algorithms decrease the latency of beamforming procedures and elevate the efficiency of smart antennas [1]. By applying adaptive beamforming (ABF), the antenna can dynamically steer the main lobe of its radiation pattern towards the direction of a desired incoming signal (i.e., signal of interest or SoI) while placing nulls towards the directions of interfering signals (i.e., signals of avoidance or SoA) to minimize the signal-to-interference-plus-noise-ratio (SINR). This process must be repeated every time changes occur in either AoA of SoI or AoAs of respective SoAs. In this study, we attempt to bypass the accurate but computationally expensive ABF techniques by using Neural Networks (NNs). Despite their training being a time-consuming process, it can be performed offline without delaying the actual NN operation.

II. NULL STEERING BEAMFORMER (NSB)

The ABF main process can be found in [2]. The NSB algorithm is very accurate regarding null placement towards interference directions with near-zero angular deviations from the desired positions as shown in [3]. This accuracy also extends to the positioning of the main lobe. In this study, a modified version of NSB based on a realistic antenna array (shown in [3]) was used as a base model for the NN training.

III. DATASET PRODUCTION - PROBLEM CONDITIONS

The antenna array of this study consists of 16 elements, where each element is excited with a complex feeding weight

(16 real and 16 imaginary parts). Therefore, 32 weight numbers are needed to produce the radiation pattern. Training and evaluation of NNs are performed using data derived from an NSB algorithm. To produce such data, some restrictions concerning the desired AoAs and their deviations from the actual AoAs are applied. Firstly, the incoming AoAs must lie within the angular sector $[30^\circ, 150^\circ]$ and have a minimum distance of $\Delta\theta = 6^\circ$ between each other. Secondly, we only keep cases, where the weights derived by the NSB algorithm produce a radiation pattern that has a main lobe deviation $< 1^\circ$ and null placement deviations $< 0.1^\circ$. Correspondingly, we expect the outputs of our final model to perform similarly, within a small margin of error, so as to consider the NN implementation successful. Finally, the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) will be 0 dB, thus considering high noise conditions.

Hence, the produced data set consists of inputs and outputs where the inputs are the polar AoAs θ_n ($n = 0, 1, \dots, N$) with the first one (θ_0) corresponding to SoI and the rest of them to SoAs, while the outputs are the 32 weight numbers created by the NSB algorithm. So, 5e6 records are created for the training of each NN variation, whereas 1.1e4 records will be used in the process of searching the best model architecture. To speed up the process of searching the best architecture for each type of NN, we assume the simple case of 1 SoI and 2 SoAs.

IV. FEED FORWARD APPROACH (FFNN)

In the case of FFNNs, AoAs are loaded at the input layer of the FFNN in parallel and are consequently processed by the neurons of the hidden layers. The NN outputs 32 values, which represent the real and imaginary parts of the complex feeding weights. In order to find the best architecture for this type of NN we perform grid search with 5-fold cross validation to figure out the best combination of number of hidden layers and

their respective sizes. Later on, another grid search is applied to figure out the best hyperparameter tuning concerning the batch-size and the learning rate. The best architecture is found to be composed of an input layer with a size of 3, an output layer with a size of 32, and four hidden layers with respective sizes equal to 256, 512, 512 and 1024.

V. RECURRENT NN APPROACH

For each time step ($t=1,2,3$), the current AoA input x_t is processed by the RNN's processing units to influence their hidden states, which are consequently passed on to the next time step units to use. In this way, each input affects the outcome of the RNN. Once all inputs are processed, and the output o_3 has been produced, the next sample inputs enter the input layer for the training process to continue (as shown in Fig. 1). The basic idea is to have the weight vector initially configured based on the desired AoA and then, as interferences enter the RNN, to shape the final form of the RNN's output by letting the AoAs of SoAs assist with the null-placement problem. Two different RNN variations based on the processing units LSTM and GRU are tested. For both cases, the best architecture includes 4 hidden layers with a size of 512 each and this is found after extensive grid search testing.

$h_i^{(j)}$: Hidden State of time step i on j -th Layer

$c_i^{(j)}$: Cell State of time step i on j -th Layer

Fig. 1. N- Layer RNN, LSTM Implementation.

VI. COMPARISON BETWEEN NN TYPES AND NSB AND EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED MODEL

Due to the significantly shorter training and mean response time and the low values of main lobe and null deviations, we choose GRU-RNN as the best possible solution. For the purpose of its evaluation, we have produced a new dataset using the NSB algorithm for cases of 3 to 10 incoming SoAs. The results proving the model's accuracy are shown in Table II. An indicative radiation pattern is also provided in Fig. 2, where AoA of SoI is equal to 100° while 10 SoAs are placed at AoAs equal to $30^\circ, 40^\circ, 50^\circ, 60^\circ, 80^\circ, 110^\circ, 120^\circ, 130^\circ, 140^\circ, 150^\circ$.

TABLE I
COMPARISON BETWEEN ALL NN MODELS AND NSB

	Mean divergence of main lobe ($^\circ$)	Mean divergence of nulls ($^\circ$)	Mean SINR (dB)	Training time (hours)	Mean response time (sec)
NSB	0.437	0.000	27.196	-	1.47
FFNN	0.438	0.364	26.530	13.28	0.00033
LSTM-RNN	0.446	0.072	27.159	18.12	0.00481
GRU-RNN	0.435	0.076	27.156	14.83	0.00469

TABLE II
NSB/ GRU-RNN PERFORMANCE COMPARISON

SoAs	Mean deviation of Main Lobe (degrees)		Mean deviation of Nulls (degrees)		Mean SINR (dB)	
	NSB	RNN	NSB	RNN	NSB	RNN
3	0.427	0.427	0.00	0.098	27.27	27.19
4	0.420	0.422	0.00	0.095	27.33	27.22
5	0.416	0.415	0.00	0.096	27.36	27.24
6	0.413	0.415	0.00	0.096	27.40	27.26
7	0.412	0.412	0.00	0.110	27.42	27.21
8	0.412	0.418	0.00	0.127	27.42	27.10
9	0.418	0.418	0.00	0.141	27.39	26.99
10	0.425	0.428	0.00	0.152	27.33	26.82

Fig. 2. NSB and GRU-RNN radiation patterns for 10 SoAs.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research was supported by the European Union, partially through the Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Innovative Training Networks Programme "Mobility and Training for beyond 5G Ecosystems (MOTOR5G)" under grant agreement no. 861219, and partially through the Horizon 2020 Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange Programme "Research Collaboration and Mobility for Beyond 5G Future Wireless Networks (RECOMBINE)" under grant agreement no. 872857.

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